

Some Applications of a Lower Bound of the First Zagreb Index of a Graph

Rao Li

Dept. of Computer Science, Engineering, and Math
University of South Carolina Aiken
Aiken, SC 29801
USA

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Abstract

The first Zagreb index of a graph G is defined as the sum of the squares of the vertex degrees of G . The main result in “R. Li, A lower bound for the first general Zagreb index of a graph, *Mathematical Aspects of Topological Indices* 5(1) 2023, 1-4” has a corollary on the lower bound of the first Zagreb index of a graph G . Using that lower bound and other established results, we in this note present sufficient conditions for some Hamiltonian properties of the line graph of a graph. We also present a lower bound of the number of triangles in a graph and an upper bound of the number of edges of a graph which does not contain a triangle as a subgraph.

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1 Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notation and terminology not defined here follow those in [2]. Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with $n(G)$ vertices and $e(G)$ edges, the degree of a vertex v is denoted by $d_G(v)$. We use $\delta(G)$ to denote the minimum degree of G . A set of vertices in G is independent if the vertices in the set are pairwise nonadjacent. A maximum independent set in G is an independent set of largest possible size. The independence number, denoted $\beta(G)$, of G is the cardinality of a maximum independent set in G . The line graph of a graph G is denoted by $L(G)$. A complete graph of order three is also called a triangle. A graph G is called claw-free if G does not contain $K_{1,3}$ as an induced subgraph. It is well-known that every line graph is claw-free. A cycle C in a graph G is called a Hamiltonian cycle of G if C contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called Hamiltonian if G has a Hamiltonian cycle. A path P in a graph G is called a Hamiltonian path of G if P contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called traceable if G has a Hamiltonian path.

The first Zagreb index was introduced by Gutman and Trinajstić in [4]. For a graph G , its first Zagreb index is defined as $M_2 := \sum_{v \in V} d_G^2(v)$. Li and Zheng in [7] further extended the first Zagreb index of a graph and introduced the concept of the first general Zagreb index of a graph. The first general Zagreb index, denoted $M_\alpha(G)$, of a graph G is defined as $\sum_{v \in V} d_G^\alpha(v)$, where α is a real number such that $\alpha \neq 0$ and $\alpha \neq 1$. Li in [6] obtained the following result on the lower bound of M_α .

Theorem 1 Let G be a graph with n vertices, e edges, and $\delta \geq 1$. Assume α is a real number such that $\alpha > 1$. Then

$$M_\alpha \geq \beta\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n - \beta)^{\alpha-1}}.$$

Equality holds if and only if G is a graph satisfying the following conditions. For any maximum independent set I in G , $d(u) = \delta$ if $u \in I$, $V - I$ is independent and $d(v) = \delta_1 \geq \delta$ if $v \in V - I$, and $e = \beta\delta = (n - \beta)\delta_1$.

Theorem 1 has the following corollary.

Corollary 2 Let G be a graph with n vertices, e edges, and $\delta \geq 1$. Then

$$M_2 \geq \beta\delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{(n-\beta)}.$$

Equality holds if and only if G is a graph satisfying the following conditions. For any maximum independent set I in G , $d(u) = \delta$ if $u \in I$, $V - I$ is independent and $d(v) = \delta_1 \geq \delta$ if $v \in V - I$, and $e = \beta\delta = (n - \beta)\delta_1$.

Using Corollary 2 and established results in [5], we in this note present sufficient conditions for some Hamiltonian properties of the line graph of a graph. We also present a lower bound of the number of triangles in a graph and an upper bound of the numbers of edges of a graphs which does not contain a triangle as a subgraph. Below are results in this paper.

Theorem 3 Let G be a 2-edge connected graph with n vertices and $e \geq 24$ edges. If

$$\delta \geq \sqrt{\frac{1}{\beta} \left(\frac{(n-\beta-1)e^2}{(n-\beta)} - 11e + 68 \right)},$$

then $L(G)$ is Hamiltonian.

Theorem 4 Let G be a 1-edge connected graph with n vertices and $e \geq 12$ edges. If

$$\delta \geq \sqrt{\frac{1}{\beta} \left(\frac{(n-\beta-1)e^2}{(n-\beta)} - 5e + 20 \right)},$$

then $L(G)$ is traceable.

Theorem 5 Let G be a graph with n vertices, e edges, and $\delta \geq 1$. Suppose t is the number of triangles in G . Then

$$t \geq \frac{1}{3} \left(\beta\delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{n-\beta} - en \right)$$

with equality if and only if G is $K_{\beta, n-\beta}$.

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Theorem 6 Let G be a graph with n vertices, e edges, and $\delta \geq 1$. Suppose G does not contain a triangle as a subgraph. Then

$$e \leq \frac{(n - \beta)n + \sqrt{(n - \beta)((n - \beta)n^2 - 4\beta\delta^2)}}{2}$$

with equality if and only if G is $K_{\beta, n-\beta}$.

2 Lemmas

We will use the following results as our lemmas. The first one is from Theorem 6.7 on Page 89 in [1]. See also [3].

Lemma 1 [3] Let G be a graph on $n \geq 3$ vertices. Suppose k is a positive integer. If G is k -edge connected, then $L(G)$ is k -connected.

Lemma 2 below follows from Theorem 1.2 on Page 2775 in [5].

Lemma 2 [5] Let G be a 2-connected claw-free graph on $n(G) \geq 24$ vertices. If $e(G) \geq (n(G) - 6)(n(G) - 7)/2 + 13$, then G is Hamiltonian.

Lemma 3 below follows from Theorem 1.4 on Page 2776 in [5].

Lemma 3 [5] Let G be a connected claw-free graph on $n(G) \geq 12$ vertices. If $e(G) \geq (n(G) - 3)(n(G) - 4)/2 + 4$, then G is traceable.

3 Proofs

Proof of Theorem 3 Let G be a graph satisfying the conditions in Theorem 3. From Lemma 1, we have that $L(G)$ is a 2-connected claw-free graph such that $n(L(G)) = e \geq 24$. Notice that

$$\begin{aligned} e(L(G)) &= \sum_{u \in V(G)} \frac{d(u)(d(u) - 1)}{2} = \frac{M_2}{2} - e \geq \frac{1}{2} \left(\beta\delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{(n - \beta)} \right) - e \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(n - \beta - 1)e^2}{(n - \beta)} - 11e + 68 + \frac{e^2}{(n - \beta)} \right) - e \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{e^2 - 13e + 68}{2} = \frac{(e-6)(e-7)}{2} + 13 \\
&= \frac{(n(L(G)) - 6)(n(L(G)) - 7)}{2} + 13.
\end{aligned}$$

From Lemma 2, we have that $L(G)$ is Hamiltonian.

This completes the proof of Theorem 3.

Proof of Theorem 4 Let G be a graph satisfying the conditions in Theorem 4. From Lemma 1, we have that $L(G)$ is a connected claw-free graph such that $n(L(G)) = e \geq 12$. Notice that

$$\begin{aligned}
e(L(G)) &= \sum_{u \in V(G)} \frac{d(u)(d(u)-1)}{2} = \frac{M_2}{2} - e \geq \frac{1}{2} \left(\beta \delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{(n-\beta)} \right) - e \\
&\geq \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(n-\beta-1)e^2}{(n-\beta)} - 5e + 20 + \frac{e^2}{(n-\beta)} \right) - e \\
&= \frac{e^2 - 7e + 20}{2} = \frac{(e-3)(e-4)}{2} + 4 \\
&= \frac{(n(L(G)) - 3)(n(L(G)) - 4)}{2} + 4.
\end{aligned}$$

From Lemma 3, we have that $L(G)$ is traceable.

This completes the proof of Theorem 4.

Proof of Theorem 5 The following paragraph is from the proofs of Theorem 2.1 on Page 218 in [8]. For each edge $e = uv$ in G , let $t(e)$ be the number of triangles on which e lies. Then $\sum_{e \in E} t(e) = 3t$, and $d(u) + d(v) \leq n + t(e)$. Then

$$M_2 = \sum_{x \in V} d^2(x) = \sum_{e=uv \in E} (d(u) + d(v)) \leq \sum_{e=uv \in E} (n + t(e)) = ne + 3t.$$

Applying Corollary 1, we have

$$ne + 3t \geq \beta \delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{(n-\beta)}.$$

Therefore

$$t \geq \frac{1}{3} \left(\beta\delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{n-\beta} - ne \right).$$

If G is $K_{\beta, n-\beta}$, then $t = 0$. Since $V - I$ is independent, $|V - I| \leq \beta$. Thus $\delta = n - \beta$. A simple computation yields that

$$\frac{1}{3} \left(\beta\delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{n-\beta} - ne \right) = 0.$$

Thus

$$t = \frac{1}{3} \left(\beta\delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{n-\beta} - ne \right).$$

If

$$t = \frac{1}{3} \left(\beta\delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{n-\beta} - ne \right),$$

we, from the proofs above, have that $d(u) + d(v) = n + t(e)$ for each $e = uv \in E$ and

$$M_2 = \beta\delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{n-\beta}.$$

From Corollary 1, we have that G is a graph satisfying the following conditions.

For any maximum independent set I in G , $d(u) = \delta$ if $u \in I$, $V - I$ is independent and $d(v) = \delta_1 \geq \delta$ if $v \in V - I$, and $e = \beta\delta = (n - \beta)\delta_1$.

Obviously, $t(e) = 0$ for each $e \in E$. Let I be a maximum independent set in G . For each vertex y in $V - I$, there exists one vertex $x \in I$ such that $yx \in E$ otherwise I wouldn't be a maximum independent set I in G . Thus we have that

$$n = n + t(yx) = d(y) + d(x) \leq |I| + n - |I| = n.$$

Therefore $d(y) = |I|$ and $d(x) = n - |I|$. Hence $yz \in E$ for each $z \in I$ and $yz \in E$ for each $y \in V - I$ and each $z \in I$. So G is $K_{\beta, n-\beta}$.

This completes the proof of Theorem 5.

Proof of Theorem 6 Let I be maximum independent set I in G . Choose a vertex u in I . Then $\delta \leq d(u) \leq n - |I| = n - \beta$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} (n - \beta)n^2 - 4\beta\delta^2 &\geq \delta n^2 - 4\beta\delta^2 = \delta(n^2 - 4\beta\delta) \\ &= \delta((\beta + n - \beta)^2 - 4\beta\delta) \geq \delta((\beta + \delta)^2 - 4\beta\delta) = \delta(\beta - \delta)^2 \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Letting $t = 0$ in Theorem 5, we have the following inequality.

$$0 \geq \frac{1}{3} \left(\beta\delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{n - \beta} - en \right).$$

Solving the quadratic equation on e , we have that

$$e \leq \frac{(n - \beta)n + \sqrt{(n - \beta)((n - \beta)n^2 - 4\beta\delta^2)}}{2}.$$

If G is $K_{\beta, n-\beta}$, then G is triangle-free. A simple computation yields that

$$e = \beta(n - \beta) = \frac{(n - \beta)n + \sqrt{(n - \beta)((n - \beta)n^2 - 4\beta\delta^2)}}{2},$$

If

$$e = \frac{(n - \beta)n + \sqrt{(n - \beta)((n - \beta)n^2 - 4\beta\delta^2)}}{2},$$

then

$$ne = \beta\delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{n - \beta}.$$

Recall that

$$\begin{aligned} \beta\delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{n - \beta} &\leq M_2 = \sum_{x \in V} d^2(x) = \sum_{e=uv \in E} (d(u) + d(v)) \\ &\leq \sum_{e=uv \in E} (n + t(e)) = ne + 3t. \end{aligned}$$

Since G is triangle-free, $t = 0$. Thus

$$ne = \beta\delta^2 + \frac{e^2}{n - \beta} = M_2 = \sum_{x \in V} d^2(x)$$

$$= \sum_{e=uv \in E} (d(u) + d(v)) = \sum_{e=uv \in E} (n + t(e)) = ne.$$

Therefore $d(u) + d(v) = n + t(e) = n$ for each $e = uv \in E$. Repeating some arguments in the proofs of Theorem 5, we can show that G is $K_{\beta, n-\beta}$.

This completes proof of Theorem 6.

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